

Original Research Article

Effect of Ledermix Paste versus Calcium Hydroxide on Inter-Appointment Pain during Root Canal Therapy

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Abstract

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Endodontic post-treatment pain is one of the significant problems faced by the dentist. In patients with necrotic teeth and acute apical periodontitis inter-appointment pain during root canal treatment is a common finding. The objective of the study is to compare the efficacy of Ledermix paste and Calcium hydroxide on inter-appointment pain during root canal treatment in patients with acute apical periodontitis. In this comparative prospective study trial, sixty patients who were undergoing dental treatment in Islamic international dental hospital, Islamabad were selected after fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria. All patients were randomly allocated in two groups. Group 1: consists of 30 patients and were treated with Ledermix paste while Group 2: include 30 patients treated with Calcium hydroxide for inter-appointment pain during root canal treatment. All Patients were interviewed regarding pain during the inter-appointment period. Visual analogue scale (VAS) was used to record pain in every patient. Independent samples t-test was used to compare mean pain score in two groups. The minimum pain score among patients was 1 and maximum was 4 with mean and standard deviation 2.95 ± 1.01 . There was a significant difference found between pain score and groups i.e. Group 1 (Ledermix paste), Group 2 (Calcium hydroxide) with p-value < 0.001. Both Ledermix and Calcium hydroxide reduces the inter appointment pain in patients but Ledermix paste is more effective in pain control. Recommendation for the intracanal medicament i.e. Ledermix should be used in routine endodontic therapy.

Keywords: Calcium hydroxide, Endodontic therapy, Ledermix paste, Root canal treatment

INTRODUCTION

Pain is the most common reason for dentist consultations. It is a main symptom in many medical and dental conditions and can significantly impede a person's quality of life and general functioning (Reivik et al., 2008). It has been reported that up to 80% of the population will continue to report pain after endodontic treatment, with pain levels ranging from mild to severe. Toothache is the most common form of oral pain (Martin and Cunningham, 2003). Root canal treatment procedure includes access cavity preparation, canal instrumentation, irrigation, intra-canal medicaments and root filling in an attempt to eradicate infection from the root canal system.

The aim of endodontic therapy is to eliminate bacteria from the root canal system and to prevent the re-growth of residual microbes (Konagala et al., 2019). Endodontic pain may occur before, during, or after endodontic treatment. Patients with moderate to severe pain before treatment were five times more likely to experience moderate to severe post treatment pain. Intra-canal medicaments have long been used to augment the mechanical procedure. Literature shows that mechanical debridement alone is not sufficient to decrease inter-appointment pain and recommends the usage of intra-canal medicament (Holstein et al., 2002). Other studies

have contraindicated this approach and reported no significant decrease in inter-appointment pain with use of canal medicaments (Torabinejad et al., 1988). Extrusion of infected debris to the periradicular tissues during chemo-mechanical preparation is allegedly one of the principal causes of postoperative pain (Siqueira, 2003).

Several intra-canal medicaments have been introduced in recent years. One of these is the "Ledermix paste" which is a combination of triamcinolone and demeclocycline. The combination has anti-inflammatory, antibacterial and anti-resorptive properties. The LEDERMIX® materials were developed in 1960 by Prof. Andre Schroeder from Switzerland. There is a paste form and a cement form of this material. Both of these materials have been widely researched and used extensively in clinical practice since becoming commercially available in 1962. Although the two forms of Ledermix have different uses in Dentistry, they have two common active components, triamcinolone (a corticosteroid) and demeclocycline (a tetracycline antibiotic) (Negm, 2001). LEDERMIX® 1g paste contains: 30.21mg demeclocycline calcium (equivalent to 30mg demeclocycline hydrochloride) 10mg triamcinolone acetate. Excipients: 3mg sodium sulphite anhydrous.

Calcium hydroxide has been used by dentists in clinical practice for over a century (Baker and Fotos, 1994). Calcium hydroxide is a white odourless powder with the chemical formula $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and a molecular weight of 7.08. Chemically, it is classified as a strong base in contact with aqueous fluids (its pH is about 12.5 - 12.8), and dissociate into Calcium and Hydroxyl ions (Fuks, 2008). The antibacterial activity of Calcium hydroxide is a major concern to most of the scientists. Cook et al. (2007) evaluated the quality of root canal filling with or without Calcium hydroxide application prior to the root canal filling or 2% Chlorhexidine on the persistence of bacterial infection on the dentinal tubules, they found that the use of 2% Chlorhexidine followed by root canal filling was more effective in removing the bacterial infection especially *E.faecalis* than placement of Calcium hydroxide or immediate canal filling (Cook et al., 2007).

The rationale of this study was to compare and find out which intra-canal medicament is effective in reducing the inter-appointment pain after the instrumentation of the root canals. So that, the distressing experience of postoperative pain may be reduced and patients will show more compliance towards the endodontic treatment (Kronicjelena et al., 2019).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This comparative prospective study was conducted at our Patient Department of Operative Dentistry at Islamic international dental hospital, Islamabad from March 2016 to Sep 2016. The sample size was calculated by using

statistical software (SPSS version 17) whereas the sampling technique was non-probability consecutive sampling. The inclusion criteria were Patients of either gender, 15-50 years of age, Symptomatic mandibular posterior teeth with a diagnosis of acute apical periodontitis and those who are willing to undergo endodontic treatment. While the exclusion criteria were teeth with a fluctuant facial swelling (acute apical abscess, malposed teeth in which access opening and instrumentation would be compromised, immature root apices because treatment option require some additional steps like apexification or apexogenesis, patients having severe periodontitis with grade 3 mobility because of poor prognosis and conditions in which conventional root canal treatment is contraindicated e.g. Vertical tooth fractures. Total 60 patients after selection were randomly allocated into two groups. Group 1: Ledermix paste (30 patients) and Group 2: Calcium hydroxide (30 patients). This study was conducted after approval of the ethical review committee of the institution. All endodontic treatment procedures were performed by the principal investigator.

After administration of Local anesthesia; teeth were isolated with the rubber dam. Carious lesion was removed, and coronal access was gained. After canal preparation and drying, following medicament was placed into the canal by Lentulo-spiral in groups randomly allocated by using Lottery method: Group 1: Ledermix Paste Group 2: Calcium hydroxide. To avoid recontamination of the canal, the access cavity was sealed with cavit, each patient was given an evaluation sheet and visual analogue pain scale was explained. The patient was self-recording pain scores. Patients were interviewed regarding any pain during the inter appointment period after 48 hours. The visual analogue scale (VAS) is a simple and frequently used method for the assessment of variations in intensity of pain scored from (Ahmed et al., 2019; Alarbeed, 2019). (Figure 1)

Data was entered and analyzed using SPSS version 17. Descriptive statistics was calculated for both qualitative and quantitative variables. For quantitative variables like age and pain scores mean \pm SD were calculated. For qualitative variables like gender frequency and percentage were calculated. Independent samples t-test was used to compare mean pain score in two groups. Effect modifiers like age and gender were controlled by stratification. Post stratification independent sample t-test was applied. P-value < 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

A total of 60 patients (30 in each group) were included in the study. Male patients in the study were 32 (53.3%) while female patients were 28 (46.7%). Mean age of the patients were 31.38 ± 9.93 years. The minimum age was found to be 17 years and maximum age was 50 years

Figure 1. The visual analogue scale (VAS)

Table 1. Mean age and pain score in patients (n = 60)

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	17	50	31.38	9.93
Pain score	1	4	2.95	1.01

Table 2. Comparison of Mean Pain Score in both groups(Independent T-test applied)

	Pain Score		P-Value
	N	Mean \pm SD	
Group 1 Ledermix paste	30	2 \pm 0.37	<0.001
Group 2 Calcium hydroxide	30	3.9 \pm 0.3	

Table 3. Comparison of Mean Pain Score in both groups with respect to Age(Independent T-test applied)

Age	Groups	Pain score		P-Value
		N	Mean \pm SD	
< 35 years	Group 1 Ledermix paste	18	1.95 \pm 0.42	0.001
	Group 2 Calcium hydroxide	21	3.90 \pm 0.3	
\geq 35 years	Group 1 Ledermix paste	12	2.08 \pm 0.29	0.001
	Group 2 Calcium hydroxide	9	3.89 \pm 0.33	

Table 4. Comparison of Mean Pain Score in both groups with respect to gender (Independent T-test applied)

Gender Groups		Pain Score		P-Value
		N	Mean \pm SD	
Male	Group 1 Ledermix paste	16	2.0 \pm 0.01	0.01
	Group 2 Calcium hydroxide	16	4.0 \pm 0.1	
Female	Group 1 Ledermix paste	14	2.0 \pm 0.55	0.01
	Group 2 Calcium hydroxide	14	3.79 \pm 0.42	

The minimum pain score was 1 and maximum was 4 with mean and standard deviation 2.95 ± 1.01 as shown in table 1.

Comparison of mean pain score after 48 hours reveals statistically significant difference between group-I and group-II (2 ± 0.37 VS 3.9 ± 0.3) with p-value < 0.001 as shown in table 2

Comparisons of mean difference of inter-appointment pain between age groups is shown in Table 3. Comparisons of mean difference of inter-appointment pain between groups with respect to male and female are presented in Table 4.

DISCUSSION

The objective of the present research was to compare the effect of Ledermix paste and Calcium hydroxide on inter-appointment pain during root canal treatment in patients with acute apical periodontitis. Studies have reported frequencies of inter-appointment emergencies ranging from 1.4% to 16% (Becker and Phero, 2005). Certain factors have been suggested to significantly influence the development of inter-appointment pain, including age, gender, tooth type, pulpal status, presence of preoperative pain, allergies, and presence of sinus tract (Walton and Fouad, 1992). In addition, fear of dental treatment, anxiety, apprehension, and possibly other psychological factors are known to influence the patient's pain perception and reaction thresholds (Imura and Zuolo, 1995).

The purpose of intra-canal medicaments is to act as an adjuvant therapy to resolve the infection. Ledermix (triamcinolone and dimethyl chlortetracycline in a water-soluble cream) is used for pulp capping, pulpal exposures, and as an intra-canal medicament in cases with pericementitis reported by Ehrmann. He concluded that Ledermix stopped the pain. According to Ehrmann et al., the patients with Ledermix paste intra-canal medicament experienced significantly less 9.5 ± 14.6 postoperative pain than with no intra-canal medicament 16.3 ± 20.8 at 48 hours (Ehrmann et al., 2003).

According to Kundbala et al. (2014) Ledermix paste act as an intra-canal medicament in endodontic cases of continuous post endodontic pain after complete pulpal extirpation or root canal system. They claimed pain relief in these cases within minutes to a few hours after the placement of Ledermix paste.

Our study results match the study conducted by Mohammadi Z et al. who claimed that Ledermix paste is better intra-canal dressing material as compare to $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ as later is resisted by refractory bacteria. He also concluded that Ledermix is more effective medicament as it contains potent anti-inflammatory and anti-resorptive properties (Mohammadi et al., 2006). On the contrary Trope reported there is no significant difference when different medicaments like; Ledermix paste, Calcium hydroxide and Formocresol are used (Trope et al., 1999).

Our results also match with the findings of Pickenpaugh who also observed that there was no direct relationship between the inter-appointment pain and gender of the patient (Pickenpaugh et al., 2001). On the contrary to our findings, some studies have shown that females are more prone to develop inter-appointment pain as compared to males (Fox et al., 1970; Morse et al., 1987).

In the present study, there was a significant difference found between pain score and groups i.e. Group 1 (Ledermix paste), Group 2 (Calcium hydroxide) with p-value < 0.001 . In both groups of age (< 35 years and ≥ 35 years), there was a significant difference found between both groups and pain score having p-value=0.001).

According to Balban the percentage of cases of acute exacerbation of inter-appointment pain decreased with advancing age because in old age the pulp canal size decreases significantly. Thus there would be a decreased volume of debris; reduced flow of blood to the alveolus and thus reduced inflammatory response to infection (Balban et al., 1984). A prospective randomized trial, conducted by Morse et al., concluded that no direct or indirect relationship could be established between incidence of inter-appointment pain and age of the patient (Morse et al., 1987). On the contrary some researchers concluded that patients above 50 years of age are more

prone to develop inter-appointment flare-up because the cementum deposition increases with age. So, coronal transportation of radiographic apex is one possibility. This would lead to increased possibility of developing error in determining the working length. Consequently, apical extrusion of the debris would occur. Thus, patients in old age have more chances of developing inter-appointment flare-up than younger patients. But this could not be verified in our study as the maximum age of the patients included in our study was 50 years.

CONCLUSION

Both Ledermix paste and Calcium hydroxide reduces the inter appointment pain in patients but Ledermix paste is more effective in pain control. Recommendation for the intra-canal medicament i.e. Ledermix paste should be used in routine endodontic therapy.

LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

Our study had limitations that it was not multi-centred and study design, was not randomized control so exceptional level of accuracy could not be achieved.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This study has no conflict of interest to be declared by any author.

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